

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA):IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Development And Validation Of An RP-UPLC Method For Rapid And Simultaneous Analysis Of Samidorphan And Olanzapine With An Integrated Stability Study

Pawar Chaitanya Vidyasagar *, Wale R. R. , Vivek Panchabhai

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry . Channabasweshwar Pharmacy College (Degree), Latur Maharashtra.

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 08 Sep 2024

Accepted: 12 Sep 2024

Published: 22 Sep 2024

Keywords:

Samidorphan, Olanzapine,
RP-UPLC

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.13825867

ABSTRACT

The development of a straight forward, precise, and accurate method for the simultaneous estimation of Samidorphan and Olanzapine in their dosage forms took place ACQUITY UPLC BEH C18 Column, 1.7 μ m, 2.1 mm X 100 mm, was used to run the chromatogram 0.1% OPA mobile phase containing buffer (4.6 pH): Acetonitrile, which was taken in a ratio of 55:45, was pumped through the column at a 0.2 ml/min flow rate. In this method 0.1% orthophosphoric acid was used as buffer. The temperature was kept at 30°C 264 nm was the preferred wavelength Samidorphan retention time was 0.669 minutes, while Olanzapine retention time was 0.880 minutes. Samidorphan %RSD was 0.3, while Olanzapine was found to be 0.91 % Recovery was 99.93% for Samidorphan and 100.26% for Olanzapine Samidorphan LOD and Olanzapine LOQ values were 0.05, 0.14, and 0.41, 1.24, respectively from their regression equations Samidorphan regression equation is $y = 19497x + 10313$, while Olanzapine equation is $y = 23803x + 7958.2$ The method was simple and cost-effective because retention times and run time were reduced.

INTRODUCTION

The word psychosis was introduced to the psychiatric literature in 1841 by Karl Friedrich Canstatt in his work Handbuch der Medizinischen Klinik. He used it as a shorthand for 'psychic neurosis'. At that time neurosis meant any disease of the nervous system, and Canstatt was thus referring to what was considered a psychological

manifestation of brain disease. Ernst von Feuchtersleben is also widely credited as introducing the term in 1845 as an alternative to insanity and mania.

Psychiatric disorders can manifest in a wide range of forms including:

***Corresponding Author:** Pawar Chaitanya Vidyasagar

Address: Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry . Channabasweshwar Pharmacy College (Degree), Latur Maharashtra.

Email ✉: chaitanyapawar995@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

- Mood disorders (e.g. depression, bipolar disorder)
- Anxiety disorders (e.g. generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder)
- Psychotic disorders (e.g. schizophrenia)
- Personality disorders (e.g. borderline personality disorder)

Other examples include: obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD), post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), eating disorders. These conditions often result from complex interaction between genetic, biological, environmental, and psychological factors. Diagnosis and treatment typically involve mental health professionals, such as psychiatrists or psychologists, who use criteria outlined in standardized diagnostic manuals (e.g., DSM-5 or ICD-10). It's important to approach mental health with empathy and understanding, as psychiatric disorders are medical conditions that can be effectively managed and treated with appropriate interventions, including psychotherapy, medication, or a combination of both. Seeking professional help is essential for accurate diagnosis and the development of an effective treatment plan tailored to an individual's specific needs. The combination of samidorphan and olanzapine represents an innovative approach to antipsychotic treatment, aiming to enhance therapeutic outcomes and reduce adverse effects. This study's findings will contribute to the development of optimized treatment protocols and provide a robust analytical framework for future pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic studies. By leveraging the advanced capabilities of UPLC, this research will offer high-precision data that can drive clinical decision-making and regulatory approval processes. The integration of samidorphan with olanzapine holds significant promise for addressing the metabolic side effects of antipsychotic therapy, thereby improving patient adherence and overall treatment success.

The application of UPLC in this study underscores the importance of advanced analytical methods in pharmacological research, enabling precise and reliable quantification of drug concentrations and interactions. This research aims to pave the way for more effective and safer antipsychotic treatments, ultimately enhancing the quality of life for patients with schizophrenia and bipolar disorder.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials:

- Samidorphan and Olanzapine pure drugs (API), Combination Samidorphan and Olanzapine tablets (LYBALVI), Distilled water, Acetonitrile, Phosphate buffer, Methanol, Potassium dehydrogenate ortho phosphate buffer, Ortho-phosphoric acid. All the above chemicals and solvents are from Rankem.
- Instruments:
- Electronics Balance-Denver
- pH meter -BVK enterprises, India
- Ultrasonicator-BVK enterprises
- UPLC instrument used was of WATERS Acquity UPLC SYSTEM with Auto Injector and Acquity TUV detector. Software used is Empower 2.
- UV-VIS spectrophotometer PG Instruments T60 with special bandwidth of 2mm and 10mm and matched quartz was be used for measuring absorbance of Samidorphan and Olanzapine solutions.

Methods:

Diluent:

Based up on the solubility of the drugs, diluent was selected, Acetonitrile and Water taken in the ratio of 50:50.

Preparation of buffer:

0.1% OPA Buffer:

1ml of Conc Ortho Phosphoric acid was diluted to 1000ml with water.

Buffer:

0.1% OPA Buffer

Accurately take 1.0 ml of OPA in a 1000ml of Volumetric flask add about 900ml of milli-Q water added and degas to sonicate and finally make up the volume with water then added 1ml of Triethylamine then PH adjusted to 4.8 with dil. Triethylamine.

API Preparation

Preparation of Standard stock solutions: Accurately weighed 10 mg of Samidorphan, 10 mg of Olanzapine and transferred to 50 ml volumetric flask separately. 3/4 th of diluents was added to both flasks and sonicated for 10 minutes. Flasks were made up with diluents and labeled as Standard stock solution 1 and 2. (200µg/ml of Samidorphan and 200µg/ml of Olanzapine)

Preparation of Standard working solutions (100% solution): 1ml from stock solution was pipetted out and taken into a 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent. (20µg/ml Samidorphan and 20µg/ml of Olanzapine)

Formulation Preparation

Preparation of Sample stock solutions:

10 tablets were weighed and equivalent to 1 tablet is weighed and transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask, to this 50 ml of acetonitrile was added and sonicated. Volume was made upto 100ml with diluents and filtered through 0.45 µm or finer porosity membrane filter (100µg/ml of Samidorphan and 100µg/ml of Olanzapine)

Preparation of Sample working solutions (100% solution):

2ml of filtered sample stock solution was transferred to 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent. (20µg/ml of Samidorphan and 20µg/ml of Olanzapine)

Validation:

System suitability parameters:

The system suitability parameters were determined by preparing standard solutions of Samidorphan (20ppm) and Olanzapine (20ppm) and the solutions were injected six times and the

parameters like peak tailing, resolution and USP plate count were determined. The % RSD for the area of six standard injections results should not be more than 2%.

Specificity:

Checking of the interference in the optimized method. We should not find interfering peaks in blank and placebo at retention times of these drugs in this method. So this method was said to be specific.

Precision:

Preparation of Sample stock solutions:

10 tablets were weighed and equivalent to 1 tablet is weighed and transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask, to this 50 ml of acetonitrile was added and sonicated. Volume was made upto 100ml with diluents and filtered through 0.45 µm or finer porosity membrane filter (100µg/ml of Samidorphan and 100µg/ml of Olanzapine)

Preparation of Sample working solutions (100% solution):

2ml of filtered sample stock solution was transferred to 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent. (20µg/ml of Samidorphan and 20µg/ml of Olanzapine)

The Repeatability was determined by preparing formulation solutions of Samidorphan (20ppm) and Olanzapine (20ppm) and the solutions were injected six times and the % RSD for the area of six standard injections results should not be more than 2%.

Linearity:

Preparation of Standard stock solutions: Accurately weighed 10 mg of Samidorphan, 10 mg of Olanzapine and transferred to 50 ml volumetric flask separately. 3/4 th of diluents was added to both flasks and sonicated for 10 minutes. Flasks were made up with diluents and labeled as Standard stock solution 1 and 2. (200µg/ml of Samidorphan and 200µg/ml of Olanzapine)

25% Standard solution:

0.25ml from standard stock solution was pipetted out and made up to 10ml. (5µg/ml of Samidorphan and 5µg/ml of Olanzapine)

50% Standard solution:

0.5ml from standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 10ml. (10µg/ml of Samidorphan and 10µg/ml of Olanzapine)

75% Standard solution:

0.75ml from standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 10ml. (15µg/ml of Samidorphan and 15µg/ml of Olanzapine)

100% Standard solution:

1.0ml from standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 10ml. (20µg/ml of Samidorphan and 20µg/ml of Olanzapine)

125% Standard solution:

1.25ml from standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 10ml. (25µg/ml of Samidorphan and 25µg/ml of Olanzapine)

150% Standard solution:

1.5ml from standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 10ml (30µg/ml of Samidorphan and 30µg/ml of Olanzapine)

Accuracy:

Preparation of Sample stock solutions: 10 tablets were weighed and equivalent to 1 tablet is weighed and transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask, to this 50 ml of acetonitrile was added and sonicated. Volume was made upto 100ml with diluents and filtered through 0.45 µm or finer porosity membrane filter (100µg/ml of Samidorphan and 100µg/ml of Olanzapine)

Preparation of Standard working solutions (100% solution):

1ml from stock solution was pipetted out and taken into a 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent. (20µg/ml Samidorphan and 20µg/ml of Olanzapine)

Preparation of 50% Spiked Solution:

1.25ml of sample stock solution was taken into a 10ml volumetric flask, to that 1.0ml from each

standard stock solution was pipetted out, and made up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of 100% Spiked Solution:

2.5ml of sample stock solution was taken into a 10ml volumetric flask, to that 1.0ml from each standard stock solution was pipetted out, and made up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of 150% Spiked Solution:

3.75ml of sample stock solution was taken into a 10ml volumetric flask, to that 1.0ml from each standard stock solution was pipetted out, and made up to the mark with diluent.

Acceptance Criteria:

The % Recovery for each level should be between 98.0 to 102

Robustness:

Small deliberate changes in method like Flow rate, mobile phase ratio, and temperature are made but there was no recognized change in the result and are within range as per ICH Guide lines. Robustness conditions like Flow minus (0.1ml/min), Flow plus (0.3ml/min), mobile phase minus, mobile phase plus, temperature minus (25°C) and temperature plus (35°C) was maintained and samples were injected in duplicate manner. System suitability parameters were not much affected and all the parameters were passed. %RSD was within the limit.

LOD sample Preparation:

0.25ml each from two standard stock solutions was pipetted out and transferred to two separate 10ml volumetric flasks and made up with diluents. From the above solutions 0.3ml each of Samidorphan, Olanzapine, solutions respectively were transferred to 10ml volumetric flasks and made up with the same diluents

LOQ sample Preparation:

0.25ml each from two standard stock solutions was pipetted out and transferred to two separate 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent. From the above solutions 0.9ml each of Samidorphan, Olanzapine, and solutions respectively were

transferred to 10ml volumetric flasks and made up with the same diluent.

Degradation studies:

Oxidation:

To 1 ml of stock solution of Olanzapine and Samidorphan, 1 ml of 20% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) was added separately. The solutions were kept for 30 min at 60°C. For UPLC study, the resultant solution was diluted to obtain 20µg/ml & 20µg/ml solution and 10 µl were injected into the system and the chromatograms were recorded to assess the stability of sample.

Acid Degradation Studies:

To 1 ml of stock solution Olanzapine and Samidorphan, 1ml of 2N Hydrochloric acid was added and refluxed for 30mins at 60°C. The resultant solution was diluted to obtain 20µg/ml & 20µg/ml solution and 10 µl solutions were injected into the system and the chromatograms were recorded to assess the stability of sample.

Alkali Degradation Studies:

To 1 ml of stock solution Olanzapine and Samidorphan, 1 ml of 2N sodium hydroxide was added and refluxed for 30mins at 60°C. The resultant solution was diluted to obtain 20µg/ml & 20µg/ml solution and 10 µl were injected into the system and the chromatograms were recorded to assess the stability of sample.

Dry Heat Degradation Studies:

The standard drug solution was placed in oven at 105°C for 1 h to study dry heat degradation. For UPLC study, the resultant solution was diluted to 20µg/ml & 20µg/ml solution and 10µl were injected into the system and the chromatograms were recorded to assess the stability of the sample.

Photo Stability studies:

The photochemical stability of the drug was also studied by exposing the 200µg/ml & 200µg/ml solution to UV Light by keeping the beaker in UV Chamber for 1 days or 200-Watt hours/m² in photo stability chamber. For UPLC study, the resultant solution was diluted to obtain 20µg/ml & 20µg/ml solutions and 10 µl were injected into the system and the chromatograms were recorded to assess the stability of sample.

Neutral Degradation Studies:

Stress testing under neutral conditions was studied by refluxing the drug in water for 1hrs at a temperature of 60°C. For UPLC study, the resultant solution was diluted to 20µg/ml & 20µg/ml solution and 10 µl were injected into the system and the chromatograms were recorded to assess the stability of the sample.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

System suitability: All the system suitability parameters were within the range and satisfactory as per ICH guidelines

Table: 1 System suitability parameters for Samidorphan and Olanzapine

S no	Samidorphan			Olanzapine			Resolution	
	Inj	RT(min)	USP Plate Count	Tailing	RT(min)	USP Plate Count		Tailing
1		0.669	4358	1.57	0.879	5212	1.53	4.6
2		0.669	4338	1.57	0.879	5201	1.53	4.6
3		0.669	4342	1.57	0.879	5206	1.53	4.6
4		0.669	4328	1.57	0.880	5180	1.52	4.6
5		0.669	4338	1.57	0.880	5182	1.52	4.6
6		0.669	4338	1.57	0.880	5182	1.52	4.6

**Validation:
Specificity:**

Figure No. 1 (a) Chromatogram of blank.

Figure No. 2 (b) Chromatogram of placebo

Figure No. 3 Chromatogram of Standard

Discussion:

Retention times of Samidorphan and Olanzapine were 0.669 min and 0.879 min respectively. We did not find and interfering peaks in blank and

placebo at retention times of these drugs in this method. So, this method was said to be specific.

Linearity:

Table 2: Linearity table for Samidorphan and Olanzapine.

Samidorphan		Olanzapine	
Conc (µg/mL)	Peak area	Conc (µg/mL)	Peak area
0	0	0	0
5	117549	5	100802
10	251713	10	210866
15	374735	15	311199
20	480704	20	395566
25	604613	25	494485
30	717706	30	596155

Fig No. 4 Calibration curve of Samidorphan

Fig No. 5 Calibration curve of Olanzapine

DISCUSSION:

Six linear concentrations of Samidorphan (5-30µg/ml) and Olanzapine (5-30µg/ml) were injected in a duplicate manner. Average areas were mentioned above and linearity equations obtained

for Samidorphan was $y = 19497x + 10313$ and of Olanzapine was $y = 23803x + 7958.2$ Correlation coefficient obtained was 0.999 for the two drugs.

Precision:

Repeatability:

Table 3 Repeatability table of Samidorphan and Olanzapine

S. No	Area of Samidorphan	Area of Olanzapine
1.	389950	478135
2.	390156	474803
3.	390117	474668
4.	386337	477670
5.	389699	476402
6.	390142	476556
Mean	389400	476372
S.D	1510.6	1427.8
%RSD	0.4	0.3

Intermediate precision (Day_ Day Precision):**Table 4 Intermediate precision table of Samidorphan and Olanzapine**

S. No	Area of Samidorphan	Area of Olanzapine
1.	386331	458541
2.	388310	463748
3.	383777	462486
4.	385163	457863
5.	382621	461809
6.	389445	467386
Mean	385941	461972
S.D	2621.2	3504.6
%RSD	0.7	0.8

Multiple sampling from a sample stock solution was done and six working sample solutions of same concentrations were prepared, each injection from each working sample solution was given on the next day of the sample preparation and obtained areas were mentioned in the above table.

Average area, standard deviation and % RSD were calculated for two drugs and obtained as 0.7% and 0.8% respectively for Samidorphan and Olanzapine. As the limit of Precision was less than "2" the system precision was passed in this method.

Accuracy:**Table 5 Accuracy table of Olanzapine**

% Level	Amount Spiked($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Amount recovered($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Recovery	Mean %Recovery
50%	10	9.94	99.43	100.26%
	10	9.99	99.94	
	10	9.97	99.65	
100%	20	20.00	100.00	
	20	19.98	99.90	
	20	20.09	100.44	
150%	30	30.42	101.38	
	30	30.55	101.83	
	30	29.92	99.75	

Table 6: Accuracy table of Samidorphan

% Level	Amount Spiked($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Amount recovered($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Recovery	Mean %Recovery
50%	10	10.04	100.42	100.41%
	10	10.02	100.18	
	10	9.98	99.84	
100%	20	19.95	99.76	
	20	20.16	100.82	
	20	19.89	99.47	
150%	30	30.25	100.84	
	30	30.38	101.27	
	30	30.33	101.09	

DISCUSSION:

Three levels of Accuracy samples were prepared by standard addition method. Triplicate injections were given for each level of accuracy and mean

%Recovery was obtained as 100.41% and 100.26% for Samidorphan and Olanzapine respectively.

Sensitivity:

Table 7 Sensitivity table of Samidorphan and Olanzapine

Molecule	LOD	LOQ
Samidorphan	0.05	0.14
Olanzapine	0.77	2.34

Robustness:

Table 8 Robustness data for Samidorphan and Olanzapine.

S.no	Condition	%RSD of Samidorphan	%RSD of Olanzapine
1	Flow rate (-) 0.1ml/min	0.8	0.3
2	Flow rate (+) 0.4ml/min	0.8	0.8
3	Mobile phase (-) 50B:50A	0.2	1.0
4	Mobile phase (+) 60B:40A	0.6	0.3
5	Temperature (-) 25°C	0.7	1.5
6	Temperature (+) 35°C	0.7	0.5

DISCUSSION:

Robustness conditions like Flow minus (0.1ml/min), Flow plus (0.4ml/min), mobile phase minus (50B:50A), mobile phase plus (60B:40A), temperature minus (25°C) and temperature plus(35°C) was maintained and samples were injected in duplicate manner. System suitability parameters were not much affected and all the

parameters were passed. %RSD was within the limit.

Assay:

Astra Zeneca pharmaceuticals (LYBALVI), bearing the label claim Samidorphan 10mg, Olanzapine 10mg. Assay was performed with the above formulation. Average % Assay for Samidorphan and Olanzapine obtained was 99.83% and 99.95% respectively

Table 9 Assay Data of Samidorphan

S.no	Standard Area	Sample area	% Assay
1	388408	391638	100.19
2	389101	388395	99.36
3	390788	390564	99.91
4	387946	389897	99.74
5	388329	390242	99.83
6	391525	390755	99.96
Avg	389350	390249	99.83
Stdev	1467.1	1081.3	0.28
%RSD	0.4	0.3	0.28

Table 9 (b) Assay Data of _Olanzapine

S. no	Standard Area	Sample area	% Assay
1	470872	473226	100.69
2	467062	465602	99.07
3	467421	472268	100.49
4	467057	471604	100.35
5	471161	465718	99.10
6	464931	464269	98.79
Avg	468084	468781	99.75
Stdev	2438.1	3993.3	0.85
%RSD	0.5	0.9	0.9

Assay was calculated by:-

$$\% \text{ Assay} = \frac{\text{AT} \times \text{WS} \times 1 \times 100 \times 10 \times \text{P} \times \text{AV}}{\text{AS} \times 50 \times 10 \times 1 \times 2 \times 100 \times \text{L.C}} \times 100$$

- AT Average Peak area of Test solution
- AS Mean peak area of standard solution
- WS Weight of working standard taken in mg
- P Assay of working standard in % on dried basis
- L.C Label Claim
- AV AVG wt of Tablet

Fig 6 (a) Chromatogram of working standard solution

Fig No.6 (b) Chromatogram of working sample solution

Degradation data

Type of degradation	Samidorphan			Olanzapine		
	AREA	%RECOVERED	% DEGRADED	AREA	%RECOVERED	% DEGRADED
Acid	380193	97.26	2.74	466966	99.36	0.64
Base	381330	97.55	2.45	466323	99.23	0.77
Peroxide	382723	97.90	2.10	462073	98.32	1.68
Thermal	387886	99.23	0.77	464908	98.92	1.08
UV	385858	98.71	1.29	465346	99.02	0.98
Water	388394	99.36	0.64	464889	98.92	1.08

Degradation chromatograms

Acid degradation chromatogram

Fig.7 acid

Base degradation chromatogram

Fig.8 base

Peroxide degradation chromatogram

Fig.9 peroxide

Thermal degradation chromatogram

Fig.10 Thermal

Uv degradation chromatogram

Fig.11. UV

Water degradation chromatogram

Fig.12.water

CONCLUSION:

A simple, accurate and precise method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of samidorphan and olanzapine in dosage form. The retention times of samidorphan and olanzapine were 0.669 minutes and 0.880 minutes, respectively. The percentage RSD for samidorphan and olanzapine were 0.3 and 0.9, respectively. The percentage yield was found to be 99.93% and 100.26% for samidorphan and olanzapine, respectively. The LOD and LOQ values obtained from the regression equations for samidorphan and olanzapine were 0.05, 0.14 and 0.41, 1.24, respectively. The regression equation for samidorphan is $y = 19497x + 10313$ and for

olanzapine $y = 23803x + 7958.2$. The storage times were reduced and the working time was reduced.

REFERENCE

1. Lalit v sonawane, bhagwat n poul, sharad v usnale, pradeepkumar v waghmare and laxman h surwase , Bioanalytical Method Validation and Its Pharmaceutical Application, Pharmaceutical Analytical Acta,2014 vol.5,pg no:1-7.
2. Sachin, L.Darkunde, Rupali,N. Borhade, Bioanalytical Method Validation: A Quality Assurance Auditor View Point asian journal of pharmaceutical technology and innovation.2017.Vol.5. pgno:59-60
3. Tijare lk, rangari nt, mahajanun, A review on bioanalytical method development and

- validation, asian journal of pharmaceutical clinical research.2016 vol.9.pgno:1-5
4. Kirthi R. Shanmugam. A review on bioanalytical method development and validation by RP – HPLC. *Journal of Global Trends in Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2014;5(4) : 2265 - 2271
 5. Richard R. Burgess. Protein precipitation techniques. *Methods in Enzymology*.2009; 463:331-341
 6. [www.mic.ucla.edu>ms_pr>proteomics](http://www.mic.ucla.edu/ms_pr/proteomics)
 7. Method development and validation skills and tricks .2019.pgno:3
 8. Pushpa Latha E, and Sailaja B, Bioanalytical Method Development and Validation by journal of medical and pharmaceutical innovation.2015 vol.1.pgno:1-9
 9. Kirthi¹, R. Shanmugam, M. Shanti Prathyusha , D. Jamal Basha, a review on bioanalytical method development and validation by rp - *Journal of Global Trends in Pharmaceutical Sciences*.2014 vol.5.
 10. Gurdeep R.Chatwal , Sham K .Anand, Instrumental Methods of Chemical Analysis , Pg 2.566-2.638 (2007)
 11. Nasal.A, Siluk.D, and Kaliszan.R. Chromatographic Retention Parameters in Medicinal Chemistry and Pharmacology, Pubmed, Vol.10, Issue 5 Pg no-381-426, March (2003)
 12. Ashok Kumar, Lalith Kishore, navpreet Kaur , Anroop Nair. Method Development and Validation for Pharmaceutical Analysis. *International Pharmaceutica Scientia*, Vol 2, Issue 3, Jul-Sep (2012)

HOW TO CITE: Pawar Chaitanya Vidyasagar , Wale R.R., Vivek Panchabhai , Development And Validation Of An RP-UPLC Method For Rapid And Simultaneous Analysis Of Samidorphan And Olanzapine With An Integrated Stability Study, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 9, 1148-1161. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13825867>